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Deliverable 5.4 – Communication and Outreach Strategy

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Executive Summary

The deliverable D5.4, entitled "Communication and Outreach Strategy and Results", presents a comprehensive communication and outreach strategy which is directly linked to the "Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results Release I" (D5.1). This deliverable provides the strategic basis for the operationalisation of the plan for exploitation and dissemination. It outlines the foundational goals and objectives related to Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) as well as provide a framework within which the project will operate.

This framework consists of components including brand positioning, stakeholder identification and outreach, identification of target audiences and the key messages which are to be conveyed to these groups, and the levels of engagement related to these stakeholders and target audiences. Furthermore, it offers a practical basis for the visual identity, brand positioning and consolidation, communication tools and channels which will be mobilised in the execution of the COOPERATE project and the various project documents which will be produced through the operationalisation of the plan for exploitation and dissemination. Regular monitoring various communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will allow the project team to evaluate the overall effectiveness and efficacy of the deployed activities and will be able to adjust this when and where necessary to reach the set goals, objectives and targets.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
R&I	Research and Innovation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
T	Task
TX.X	Task Number
WP	Work Package

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background for Communication Plan

COOPERATE's overall objective is to develop and pilot the ERA (European Research Area) Hub concept based on the vision and success stories developed within the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their Research & Innovation (R&I) ecosystems. The overall approach revolves around co-creation Arenas in which ecosystems and a broader community of quadruple helix actors interact. The piloting phases of the project aim to test the ERA Hub approach and pave the way for its consolidation and replication phase.

The approach follows a mechanism in which leverage is sought to engage a broad range of stakeholders, activate cross-fertilization, facilitate mutual understanding, create intertwining cooperation, and jointly develop innovative ideas for shaping the ERA Hub framework model for further piloting and validation. The intended ERA Hub model builds on lines of action (e.g., access to knowledge and talents) which gather various initiatives/projects to animate the actors and stakeholders and operate the ecosystem around common priorities (i.e., strategic multi-annual roadmap) which reflect the mission-based approach. In this framework the key exploitable results include: 1) The ERA Hub model and associated PLAYBOOK, TOOLBOX and PLATFORM with compliance criteria to develop the ERA Hubs network; 2); the Policy Recommendations and content from co-creation activities.

The consortium is aware that the outcome of the project is supporting the European Commission (EC) roadmap towards the launch of ERA Hubs as flagship initiative in Europe to boost the ERA, beyond the scope of the project. Tailor made communication, dissemination and exploitation actions will therefore create awareness and engagement within regional ecosystems in the European Union (EU), building consensus in a close dialogue with EU and national/regional institutions. In particular, two large events will be organised in Brussels at mid-term and at the end of the project for consensus building on the project findings and policy recommendations.

1.2 Importance of communication for the project's success

The deliverable (D) D5.1 entitled 'Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results-Release I' has been produced at the beginning of the project under WP5 and has been submitted at the end of March 2023. The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) details the actions and specific tools to be developed by all partners under Task 5.1, entitled "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Action Plan", which focuses on planning for communication and dissemination and extends throughout the whole period of the project from Month 1 to Month 30 (M1-M30).

Going forward, it is important to reiterate the distinction COOPERATE has made between communication, dissemination and outreach.

- Communication activities: These activities encompass efforts that span the entire project, including its results. Commencing from the project's inception, the focus lies on engaging the consortium, project supporting partners, media outlets, and communities both within Europe and beyond so as to achieve a multiplier effect.
- Dissemination activities: Dissemination activities are especially related to the project's results as they become available. This involves sharing information with peer groups, academia,

professional organisations and policymakers who may apply the sustainable outcomes in their work.

- **Outreach Activities:** These activities involve proactive efforts to connect and engage with specific target audiences or communities. The primary goal of outreach is to build relationships, foster trust, and create meaningful interactions with the intended recipients. This entails reaching out to the audience through various communication channels and initiatives, with the objective of forging connections, eliciting responses, and encouraging active participation.

2. Goals and Objectives

2.1 Overall communication goals of the project

COOPERATE focuses on developing an effective ERA Hub model creating the basis for a long-term impact in line with the ERA roadmap. This will require a string alignment to generate impact, from initial awareness to community outreach beyond the consortium and the duration of the project.

This communication strategy corresponds to Task 5.1 (T5.1, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan) of Work Package 5 (WP5, Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities).

One of the central objectives of this strategy is to reach the identified target groups through tools, channels and content based on project activities, developed specifically for communication and dissemination purposes. The aim is not only to keep relevant parties to the project informed, but also to expand the scope of dissemination and communication activities on target groups outside of COOPERATE current network.

The defined goals for this project have a broad scope and are the desired long-term results of this communication strategy. These goals are:

- 1 Maximum exposure of the project key facts, outputs and findings among peer groups, industries, professional organisations, policymakers as well as local communities to raise awareness, increase engagement and reach maximum impact.
- 2 Supporting the transfer of project results and engagement from key stakeholders in academia, industry, EC and its related initiatives (ERA Fabric, (RIV – Regional Innovation Valleys; PRI – Partnerships for Regional Innovation; TSSP – Thematic Smart Specialisation Platforms; RIV – Regional Innovation Valleys; PRI – Partnerships for Regional Innovation; TSSP – Thematic Smart Specialisation Platforms; RIV – Regional Innovation Valleys; PRI – Partnerships for Regional Innovation; TSSP – Thematic Smart Specialisation Platforms) to generate interest and receive validation from peers globally.
- 3 Enhancing the practical and academic potential of the results as well as users' reception and user acceptance within the EU on different government levels (local, regional, national and European).

2.2 Objectives

In order to achieve the aforementioned goals, COOPERATE must firstly define a positive and cohesive brand identity which encompasses visual elements (see chapter **Error! Reference source not found.. Error! Reference source not found.**) and communication/dissemination elements (purpose, goals and messaging). The purpose is to establish an identifiable brand across Europe that will be instantly correlated to ERA and the ERA-hub framework by COOPERATE target groups.

Secondly, the goals can be accomplished by developing communication and dissemination materials to inform the media, project partners and target groups about project significant milestones, outcomes and pertinent news. The communication and dissemination materials must always reflect the developed brand identity and voice.

Additionally, specific actions need to be taken in order to fulfil the communication goals. These required measures represent the communication objectives, which will be serve as benchmarks for evaluating the outcomes of this strategy. For COOPERATE these objectives are: 1) Heightening Awareness; 2) Brand Positioning and Consolidation; and 3) Promoting Transferability & Uptake.

- 1 **Heightening Awareness** – Information and informative content will be regularly made available within the consortium as well as to close/aligned partners. Additionally, the informative content will also be shared with target groups possessing limited or no knowledge of COOPERATE. In order to convey the intended message, it is of utmost importance to simplify complex and/or technical terms. The aim is to increase awareness of, and familiarity with the project as well as to communicate news, activities and outcomes relating to the project.
- 2 **Brand Positioning and Consolidation** – Relationships with groups that directly benefit from COOPERATE mission must be nurtured by continuously updating them with relevant news of progress being made in order to share or reinforce foundational concepts and knowledge. In order to do so, the positioning of the COOPERATE brand is key. This helps to create better engagement with the target groups and instil a deeper understanding of the work being done, build trust in the project and subsequently help with the positioning of COOPERATE. Furthermore, the positioning of the brand can positively influence consolidation activities.
- 3 **Promoting Transferability & Uptake** – Naturally, it is important to prompt action through content development by targeting groups that are in a position to adapt the results to their local ecosystem and adopt an approach and/or output offered by the project. An increased satisfaction rate will result in increased commitment from current and potential partners , consequently enhancing the reception of the project results and yielding a higher likelihood of transferability and policy uptake through gained recognition and commitment from target groups.

2.3 Stakeholder engagement and outreach process

Stakeholder engagement is important for every project but perhaps particularly so for COOPERATE, where the participation of diverse stakeholders and actors is core to the project and crucial for successfully achieving its objectives. The following framework shows the process to effectively involve the different stakeholders into the various activities of the project.

Figure 1: Stakeholder engagement and outreach process

- 1 Stakeholder Identification & Analysis:** Stakeholder identification & analysis is the initial phase of stakeholder management and aims to identify all individuals, groups, or organisations that have an interest in or are affected by the project or initiative. The goal is to comprehensively map and understand these stakeholders to ensure that no relevant parties are overlooked.
- 2 Stakeholder Engagement:** Stakeholder engagement is the active and ongoing process of involving identified stakeholders in the COOPERATE project and ERA hubs in general. This phase aims to establish meaningful and constructive relationships with stakeholders to gather input, seek feedback, and involve them in decision-making processes.
- 3 Stakeholder Management:** Stakeholder management is the process of strategizing and implementing actions to address stakeholders' interests, expectations, and concerns effectively. This phase includes the development of a clear stakeholder management plan that outlines how each stakeholder group will be managed throughout COOPERATE's duration.
- 4 Sustaining Stakeholder Engagement:** The sustainability of stakeholder engagement centers on sustaining consistent and ongoing communication and interaction with stakeholders not only during the project's life cycle but also beyond the scope of COOPERATE. This phase recognizes that stakeholder engagement is not a one-time event but a continuous effort.
- 5 Stakeholder Process Evaluation:** Stakeholder process evaluation is the assessment of the efficacy and impact of ERA hubs and the COOPERATE project as a whole. This phase involves evaluating the effectiveness of the implementation of the engagement strategies, the level of stakeholder satisfaction, and the extent to which stakeholders' inputs influenced project decisions.

3 Target audience

3.1 Stages and involvement of target audiences

As COOPERATE progresses through its different stages of activities (fully-fledged co-creation, piloting and monitoring, outreach), the involvement of targeted groups will evolve, leading to a progressive scaling-up of the project community. Each stage involves different target groups:

- **Fully-Fledged Co-Creation:** During the fully-fledged co-creation stage, the project team collaborates closely with a select group of key stakeholders, which may include:
 - Research Organisations/Institutes, Knowledge/Academic Institutes (Researchers and Innovation Practitioners): These experts actively participate in brainstorming sessions and workshops to co-create innovative ideas and solutions.
 - Businesses (Large Companies, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)) and Industrial Associations: Industry partners contribute their domain expertise and provide insights into market needs and challenges.
 - Innovation Agencies and Regional Development Agencies: These organisations may offer support and funding to facilitate the co-creation process.
 - EU, National, and Regional Policy Bodies, Governmental Institutions: Policy-makers may be engaged to ensure the project aligns with broader strategic priorities.

- **Piloting and Monitoring the ERA-Hub Model Testing:** During the piloting and monitoring stage, the project community expands to include participants involved in testing and evaluating the pilot activities. Targeted groups at this stage may include:
 - Society as a Whole, General Public, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and Associations Representing Society and Consumers: Participants from diverse backgrounds are engaged to test the viability and acceptance of the pilot initiatives within the broader community.
 - Researchers: Researchers may be involved in monitoring and evaluating the impact of the pilots, collecting data, and analysing results.
 - Banks and Investors: Financial stakeholders may participate to assess the project's potential for scaling up and its attractiveness for further investment.

- **Outreach and Scaling-Up:** During the outreach and scaling-up stage, the project community expands further to include a wider audience. Targeted groups at this stage may include:
 - Other EU and Regional Initiatives and ERA Relevant Projects: Collaboration with other relevant projects and initiatives can lead to knowledge exchange and a broader impact.
 - Governmental Institutions and Policy Bodies: Engaging with policy-makers at this stage is crucial for advocacy and the potential integration of successful practices into policies.
 - General Public and Media: Raising awareness among the general public and media can generate interest and support for the project, amplifying its reach.

Throughout the progressive scaling-up, the project's communication and outreach strategy will adapt to the changing target groups, ensuring that the right messages and activities are tailored to each stage's participants. The aim is to foster collaboration, obtain valuable feedback, and generate momentum for the project's success and impact at each stage of its development.

3.2 Key target audiences and stakeholders

In total, seven key target groups are being defined below, each with a distinct role that they can play in contributing to the project:

1. Research Organisations/Institutes, Knowledge/Academic Institutes

Researchers are professionals who conduct systematic investigations to expand knowledge in various fields, while innovation practitioners focus on driving creative problem-solving and innovation within organisations and industries. Together, they contribute to the advancement of knowledge and the implementation of novel solutions, shaping technological advancements and societal progress. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model.
- Active involvement in piloting initiatives.
- Active members of the COOPERATE community.

2. Innovation agencies, Regional Development Agencies, Legal Entities Managing the Ecosystems

These organisations play a pivotal role in fostering innovation and economic growth within specific regions or industries. They provide support, funding, and resources to innovative projects and startups, facilitate collaboration among stakeholders, and create a conducive environment for innovation to thrive. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model
- Active involvement in piloting initiatives.
- Active membership within the COOPERATE community

3. Businesses (large companies, SMEs) and Industrial Associations

Businesses, both large and small, are critical players in driving innovation. They invest in research and development, create new products and services, and contribute to economic growth. Industrial associations represent the interests of businesses within specific sectors and advocate for policies that support innovation and competitiveness. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in Tech and Innovation campaigns and company missions
- Active membership within the COOPERATE community

4. EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions

These governmental bodies and policy-makers play a crucial role in shaping the ERA hub landscape through regulations, funding programs, and policy initiatives. They formulate strategies to support

research and innovation, promote collaboration between academia and industry, and drive regional and national development. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in the consultation process with regional and national policy bodies

5. Other EU and regional initiatives and ERA relevant projects (e.g., Excellence Hubs)

Various EU and regional initiatives, including Excellence Hubs and research projects, contribute to advancing knowledge and innovation. They often focus on cutting-edge research and technology development, encouraging collaboration among researchers and practitioners across borders. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in events to share best practices relevant to the COOPERATE objectives
- Contribution to community building by leveraging on the initial Co-Design Task Force (CDTF) and piloting stakeholders

6. Society as a whole, general public, NGOs and Associations representing society and consumers

The general public, NGOs, and associations representing society and consumers are key stakeholders in the innovation process. They provide insights into societal needs and preferences, advocate for sustainable and responsible innovation, and ensure that innovations benefit the broader community.

The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub mode
- Active participants in piloting and outreach

7. Banks and investors

Banks and investors play a vital role in funding innovative projects and startups. Their financial support enables the development and commercialization of innovative ideas, driving economic growth and competitiveness. The key role they can play is:

- Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model
- Active participants in piloting
- Active members of the COOPERATE community

3.3 Different level of engagement and different roles

The above mentioned target groups and stakeholders all have different roles and thus have a different level of engagement with COOPERATE and ERA hubs. The level of engagement refers to different degrees or intensities of involvement and interaction that stakeholders have, or are required to have:

- **Inform:** At the lowest level of engagement, stakeholders of COOPERATE are only informed about the project's activities, progress, and outcomes. Information is provided through one-way communication channels, such as newsletters or social media. This level of engagement accounts for all stakeholders involved in COOPERATE.
- **Consult:** In the consultation level of engagement, stakeholders of COOPERATE are asked for their opinions, feedback, or suggestions on specific issues or decisions. The COOPERATE project team seeks input from those stakeholders to consider their perspectives before making decisions. This level is mainly linked to governmental bodies and policy-makers that play a crucial role in shaping the ERA hub landscape.
- **Involve:** Involvement level of engagement links to active participation of stakeholders in certain aspects of the project. They collaborate, share ideas, and work together with the project team on tasks or initiatives related to the project. The co-creation sessions are sessions where participants are involved to share information and input to shape the ERA hub model.
- **Collaborate:** Collaboration involves a different level of engagement, where stakeholders work closely with the project team throughout the project's duration to achieve certain goals. For instance, stakeholders that can play a role in tech and innovation campaigns, company missions or events to share best practices.
- **Empower:** At the highest level of engagement, COOPERATE stakeholders are empowered to take ownership of certain project aspects. They are given authority to lead and implement initiatives independently, with the support of the project team. These are active members in the regional innovation ecosystems and the COOPERATE project team.

3.4 Detailed description of key target audiences and stakeholders

A preliminary identification of the COOPERATE stakeholders and targeted groups is presented below with reference to the quadruple helix model:

Table 1: Overview Target Groups. Including knowledge level, interests, and communication preferences

Target group	Knowledge level	Key role/contribution	Language usage	Key benefit
Research Organisations/Institutes, Knowledge/Academic Institutes (Researchers and innovation practitioners)	As participants in R&I ecosystems, this group has limited knowledge of what it entails, but are aware of its potential and importance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model; • Active participants in piloting; • Active members of the COOPERATE community. 	Professional, must try to avoid complex ERA terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shaping an effective ERA Hub model and inter-/intra-operability mechanisms to support joint research and mobility of talents; • Knowledge-sharing.
Innovation agencies, Regional Development Agencies, Legal Entities managing the Ecosystems	This group is aware of the importance of R&I ecosystems (and ERA) but has limited knowledge of the particulars behind it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model; • Active participants in piloting; • Active members of the COOPERATE community. 	Professional, complex ERA terminology can be used to expound technical terms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering synergies with on-going local initiatives creating the link between research and innovation in their ecosystems • Reinforced representativeness at the benefit of their members; • Increased reputation through participation in high-profile reports.
Businesses (large companies, SMEs) and Industrial Associations	As participants in R&I ecosystems, this group has limited knowledge of what it entails, but are aware of its potential and importance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in Tech and Innovation campaigns and company missions; • Active members of the COOPERATE community. 	Professional, must try to avoid complex ERA terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First-hand information on a promising model to reinforce research and knowledge creation which enable future value propositions for industry competitiveness and business resilience; • Shaping the ERA Hubs agenda to foster knowledge transfer and talent mobility mechanisms which can support local businesses and their connection with champions in other regions.
EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions	More specialised decision makers have fair knowledge concerning R&I ecosystems (and ERA),	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in the consultation process with regional and national policy bodies. 	Professional, complex ERA terminology can be used to expound technical terms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kept informed about important findings of the project • Steering the project results towards an effective synergy with the whole set of ERA initiatives and initiatives built on a place-based approach at local

	its importance and potential.			scale, such as the Digital Innovation Hubs (Digital Europe Programme), European Innovation Ecosystems Action (HorizonEurope) and Interregional Innovation Investments (ERDF).
Other EU and regional initiatives and ERA relevant projects (e.g., Excellence Hubs)	This group is aware of the importance of R&I ecosystems (and ERA) but has limited knowledge of the particulars behind it.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in events to share best practices relevant to the COOPERATE objectives. • Contribute to community building by leveraging on the initial Co-Design Task Force (CDTF) and piloting stakeholders. 	Professional, complex ERA terminology can be used to expound technical terms.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-pollination and fertilisation; • Increased synergies and networks.
Society as a whole, general public, NGOs and Associations representing society and consumers	This group has poor knowledge of the intricacies pertaining to the EU, its institutions and programmes can deter this group from supporting COOPERATE. Reaching them is particularly difficult because they do not actively seek information in regard to this subject.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model; • Active participants in piloting and outreach; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Friendly, devoid of complex ERA terminology. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep the human dimension, inclusiveness, gender balance etc. as high priorities when shaping the ERA Hub model. • Early understanding on promising human centric research lines and the possible introduction of new emerging technologies.
Banks and investors	As participants in R&I ecosystems, this group has limited knowledge of what it entails, but are aware of its potential and importance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct participation in co-creation arenas to shape the ERA Hub model; • Active participants in piloting; • Active members of the COOPERATE community. 	Professional, must try to avoid complex ERA terminology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate their university-industry collaborative platforms and acceleration programmes for promising research results within the whole ERA Hub model. • Define specific tools which may support talents careers with a focus on their EU mobility as valuable asset for local economies

4 Key Messages

4.1 Segmentation of audiences for tailored communication

Once a target group has been identified, the next step is to break down the set objectives into key messages tailored to each group. These key messages must resonate with the intended audience. Continuity across the messages is crucial. They must deliver a clear understanding of what COOPERATE stands for. Therefore, all key messages link back to project objectives and values.

4.1.2 Primary messages to be communicated

Research Organisations/Institutes, Knowledge/Academic Institutes (Researchers and innovation practitioners)

- COOPERATE boosts new advances in knowledge creation and innovation paired with a human touch.
- COOPERATE contributes to European leadership in knowledge creation and academia-industry collaboration within the quadruple helix.
- COOPERATE explores the full breath of newly uncovered research lines and results, bringing them close to industry and creating places where industry and academia can meet with society and public stakeholders, foster “win-win” collaborations and speed-up the uptake of knowledge/intensive and human-centric solutions with the citizens at the core for full recognition and impact.

Innovation agencies, Regional Development Agencies, Legal Entities Managing the Ecosystems

- The envisioned ERA Hub model builds on lines of action (e.g. access to knowledge and talents) which gather a set of initiatives/projects to animate the actors and stakeholders and operate the ecosystem around common priorities (i.e. strategic multi-annual roadmap) which reflect the mission-based approach.
- In order to improve the coordination of the structures involved in knowledge production within the ERA, COOPERATE focuses along two main directions: 1) the regional ecosystems; 2) the collaboration across regional ecosystems, within the European Research Area.

Businesses (Large Companies, SMEs) and Industrial Associations

- COOPERATE will support interconnection of ecosystems and their impacts to revise business models and local practices to procure research outputs in a responsible and sustainable way, ultimately improving the security and access to EU value chains (also in case of sudden disruptions) and support open strategic autonomy of EU.

EU, national and regional policy bodies, governmental institutions

- COOPERATE focuses on strengthening internal cohesion within, and international cohesion, within the EU Member States, fostering collaborations and exchanging successful concepts between ‘strong’ and ‘weak’ ecosystems in the national territory no matter their location (be it

at city, region, country or cross-border level), thus ensuring capacity building towards excellence in the national R&I systems as a whole.

- The ERA-Hub concept framework, crafted by COOPERATE will define the operational and governance model at regional, national and EU level.
- COOPERATE contributes towards expected outcomes by testing the new ERA Hubs concept across different geographies and structures in Europe, based on common compliance criteria; the process should act as an incentive for advanced ecosystems to seek recognition, and for emerging ecosystems to reach the criteria facilitating support from European, national and regional level.

Other EU and Regional Initiatives and ERA Relevant Projects (e.g., Excellence Hubs)

- COOPERATE will test the new ERA Hubs concept with pilot EU ecosystems, based on common compliance criteria.
- COOPERATE coordinates co-creation Arenas in which ecosystems and a broader community of quadruple helix actors can interact to co-create the ERA Hub model.
- COOPERATE will launch a Call for Champions which will lead to engagement with two other ecosystems.

Society as a whole, general public, NGOs and Associations representing society and consumers

- Research and Innovation (R&I) makes a significant contribution to achieving Europe's wider policy goals and particularly to addressing transformative changes based on smart directionality.
- COOPERATE contributes to this objective by developing and piloting the ERA Hub concept based on the vision and success stories developed within the EuroTech Universities Alliance and their R&I ecosystems.
- COOPERATE fosters human centric solutions to deal with new societal needs, rapidly changing customer demands, and address ethical aspects of future value chains.

Banks and investors

- COOPERATE supports the definition of inter- and intra-operability mechanisms that will allow to align missions, priorities, lines of actions to build joint initiatives on highly promising research activities and university-industry collaborations schemes which link and connect talents, research infrastructures and opportunities.

5 Engagement and Communication Tools and Channels

Proactive engagement involves reaching out to the target audience on an ongoing basis, rather than waiting for them to initiate contact. COOPERATE will use different forms of communication to help ensure the success of the project. In order to capture and retain the attention of target groups, online and offline activities will be developed to boost engagement and increase commitment through the use of visual content (e.g., videos, podcasts, photos) as well as written content. All COOPERATE communication and dissemination content must be cohesive and reflect the established brand identity.

This approach keeps the target audience informed, interested, and connected with the project's updates and developments. Proactive engagement can also involve addressing concerns, answering questions, and sharing relevant content to maintain a strong rapport with the audience. Relevant information for target groups pertaining to COOPERATE will be distributed by way of the following communication and dissemination tools and channels: online platforms, project documentation, publications and events. COOPERATE will develop and implement the following communication tools that will allow the project to raise awareness among the stakeholders identified in the previous section:

5.1 Project branding guidelines and logos

visual identity will be developed as a tool to create branding around the project and properly convey the message of its purpose to the main stakeholders. The COOPERATE visual identity will be incorporated in all project's materials. It will contribute to the project's visibility, noticeability and relatability. Visual identity is carried out and used throughout the project in all channels:

- Website
- Logo
- MS templates
 - Font
 - Header 1: Arial, Bold, size 16. Colour: #263363
 - Header 2: Arial, size 13. Colour: #12ADD4
 - Header 3: Arial, size 12. Colour: #1F3763
 - Normal: Arial, size 10. Colour: #000000
- Flyer template
- Banners for project partner's website

All project results, communication and other material should display:

- COOPERATE logo
- Project number: 101095017
- The EU flag including text to acknowledge the support under Horizon Europe

Logo:

EU Flag:

5.2 Online communication

5.2.2 COOPERATE website

The COOPERATE website (<https://www.cooperate-project.eu/>) is the primary internal and external communication and dissemination channel. The aim is to have all information and documentation that supports the fundamental strategic goals and objectives of the project in a cohesive manner and adhering to the brand identity in a widely accessible platform. The COOPERATE website, created by STAM, is based on the WORDPRESS platform, which provides a number of useful tools and functionalities and allows the site administrator to access a number of simple site access statistics. The COOPERATE website features a design that combines a simple, straightforward layout with a graceful font, blue tones and a complementary accent colour. The responsive design ensures accessibility not only from computers, but also from mobile devices such as tablets and smartphones.

The design follows and complements the visual identity of the project. Thus, from the homepage of the site, a menu leads the user to the main features of the site (see below). The project website is complemented by a strong social media presence to promote greater awareness and interaction with external stakeholders.

The structure of the website is described in detail hereafter. The home page shows some information about the project and contains an interactive menu that the user can navigate to access the following website sections:

- Home
- About
- Material hub
- News
- Partners

More information on the website can be find in D5.3.

5.2.3 Partner Websites and Content Release

To boost the impact among (highly) specialised target groups, all consortium members and partners are expected to periodically mention their participation in COOPERATE on their organisation's website and/or social media channels.

Consortium members and partners are expected to help maximise COOPERATE's reach and impact by periodically sharing relevant content – including the promotion of met deliverables – on their own social media 'profiles'. This content will subsequently be shared on all COOPERATE publications and online platforms.

5.2.4 Social Network Platform: LinkedIn

In order to achieve the projects objective COOPERATE primarily focus on reaching its target audience through LinkedIn.

A public social network 'profile' or 'user' will be created on the aforementioned networking channels to raise awareness, increase understanding, engagement and encourage target groups to take action in regard to COOPERATE. This can not only be accomplished by publishing educational (for target groups with poor/limited knowledge of ERA) and thought-provoking content – which will develop continuously as the project moves forward – and will be released as more project outcomes are ready to be published in addition to dissemination of project results. Tagging and engaging leaders and influencers in conversations will help widen COOPERATE's reach. Gaining a large following and/or subscription is essential to establish a social network presence and maximising the project's impact on a global scale.

Social Network Hashtags, Profiles Tags and Content Description

1. **Hashtags** – These are metadata tags that will be used as a way to connect COOPERATE social media content to a specific topic, event, theme or conversation. They also make it easier to discover posts around those specific topics, because hashtags amass all social media content with that same hashtag. The following hashtag rules must be adhered to:
 - All COOPERATE content on LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube, including press releases, must always contain the following overall project hashtags: #ERA #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU #COOPERATE #innovation #ecosystems #EU
 - All COOPERATE posts shared on social network platforms that include topics relating to specific consortium member(s) must include – in addition to the aforementioned hashtags – another hashtag mentioning the involved consortium member(s), e.g.: #ConsortiumMemberX #COOPERATE #HorizonEurope #HorizonEU #innovation #ecosystems #EU
 - In addition to the aforementioned hashtags press releases must always include hashtags mentioning every consortium member individually and the related subject.
2. **Profile Tags** – Tagging specific social media profile identifies each person (representing a company/organisation) in shared posts and visual content. They also receive a notification to inform them that they have been mentioned. It also links back to that specific post and/or visual

content. This makes it easier for each tagged person (representing a company/organisation) to continue sharing COOPERATE content.

- Consortium member(s) mentioned in COOPERATE posts or appearing in visual content must always be tagged individually, e.g.: @john_doe
- When COOPERATE posts and/or visual content contains topics pertaining to specific consortium member(s), consortium member tags must be used in addition to tags of the person(s) representing it, e.g.: @consortium_member_x @john_doe
- Press releases must always include the profile tag of every consortium member individually.
- The social media profile of each person mentioned in COOPERATE posts or appearing in visual content must always be tagged. When the individual represents a company or an organisation, the company/organisation tag must be added as well.
- When COOPERATE posts and/or visual content contains topics pertaining to 'sister project' ERA Fabric they must be tagged as well, including the person appearing in said post or visual content representing the sister project.
- COOPERATE content can include the European Commission profile tag @EU_H2020 when deliverables are met.

Content description – All COOPERATE content must refer to the European Commission H2020 Research and Innovation Programme. COOPERATE content, including press releases, must always include the following: COOPERATE is funded by the European Commission H2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement 101095017 and call identifier HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-30.

5.2.5 Quarterly newsletter

A newsletter every 3 months is planned to inform the community of the progress made and next events/activities in the project, including scientific and policy related news in an easy-to-read format. The newsletter will be shared through email and archived in .pdf version on the website.

5.3 Project Documentation

5.3.1 Communication Kit

In the same logic as the podcasts, the objective is to translate sometimes difficult scientific content into content which is more easy-to-understand. To ensure widespread communication, a package containing promotional material will be designed to assist the press in telling COOPERATE's story. Additionally, it will serve as an information kit for anyone interested in learning more about COOPERATE, such as potential partners and stakeholders. The communication kit will be available digitally and in some cases in paper form. The communication kit will be utilised for specific events or occasions where COOPERATE is presented or to (re)present the broader ERA-hub scope. The following materials will be included in the (digital) communication kit:

- Factsheets (4x)
 - Toolbox (including proven/real-life examples)

- Pilot AI in Prague
- Playbook
- ...
- Flyer illustrating the COOPERATE objectives and activities
- Poster to be created at mid-term to highlight the outcomes and future outcomes of the project. The project poster will be designed as a visual tool to garner instant attention from target groups at COOPERATE events and other gatherings where consortium members will participate.

5.3.2 Press Releases

Press releases will be sent to media outlets to announce important news about the project, in particular milestones and results with the purpose to maximise exposure, consequently raising COOPERATE's profile. Short press-release style pieces of communication will be prepared at the beginning and at the end of the project and in any other moment of the project when significant milestones are achieved and events are organised.

5.3.3 Video

Three videos will be created to maximise project's impact. One of them will be created to present the project, the underlying methodology and the activities. The other two videos will be created to present co-creation activities and main achievements, to tease the upcoming COOPERATE events, and present the main outcomes of events. At the end of the project, a video showcasing the results and impacts of the project.

5.3.4 White Paper

A white paper is a comprehensive and authoritative document that presents a problem, issue, or a proposed solution in a clear and informative manner. At the end of the project, a white paper will be made which can be used by government and academia to educate readers about the project and provide recommendations.

5.4 Outreach Initiatives

This component focuses on designing and executing various outreach initiatives and events to connect with the target audience effectively. The above mentioned communication channels and tools are needed to reach the desired stakeholders. The initiatives are planned to create meaningful interactions and raise awareness about COOPERATE and ERA hubs. The aim is to share project developments and engage with target groups in order to obtain commitment, support and persuade them to participate.

5.4.1 Expert talks and Podcasts

An expert talk is a powerful outreach initiative that involves inviting subject-matter experts to share their insights, knowledge, and experiences on a specific topic with a target audience. Six expert talks webinars will be organised to bring spotlight to scientific experts, illustrate project work and activities in

the co-creation activities inspiring videos and communication to create engagement. These expert talks will be recorded and used as podcasts, to enable stakeholders to re-listen or listen at a later stage. The talks are based on the project public deliverables and above all the outcomes of COOPERATE, highlighting the main takeaways and making them 'easy-to-understand and to digest' for non-scientific stakeholders and the general public. Podcasts will be released on the most relevant podcast channels.

5.4.2 Events (workshops, seminars, webinars, conferences and networking events)

Workshops, seminars, webinars, conferences and networking events provide a dynamic platform to showcase the ideas behind COOPERATE and ERA hubs, and to interact with stakeholders. COOPERATE aims to create as many synergies as possible by joining existing events as much as possible. For instance, major events like the World Open Innovation Conference (WOIC) can be used to bring theory and practice closer together. The conference is attended by academics, industry executives and policymakers who manage open innovation in their organisations and therefore a suitable platform.

Throughout the project, COOPERATE will (co-)organise two events (in presence and if possible web-streamed) with 200+ participants from EC, regional/national bodies and ecosystems' stakeholders. The goal is to gather feedback for the piloting work and recommendations. Furthermore, delegates from COOPERATE will participate, visit and present during various other events that are related to the topic of ERA hubs and innovation ecosystems. Events will be promoted on COOPERATE and consortium members' online platforms, publications and COOPERATE's documentation. The table below shows the types of events organised by COOPERATE or where COOPERATE delegates will be present:

Table 2: Event types

Event Type	Purpose	Who	Examples
Regional or national	Events at a regional or national level with a targeted presentation to encourage action on a regional or national level	Project partners keep an eye on opportunities in their home country and participate with someone from the local (NL, DK, CZ) ecosystem	e.g. UNL <i>imited</i> September 2023 (Den Bosch, Netherlands)
European	Represent COOPERATE in European network, organise and/or attend workshops, give project related presentations, create awareness and commitment for Call for Champions, etc.	All project partners keep an eye on European opportunities and participation will be done by rep. from COOPERATE project	e.g. EuroTech Summer Reception, EuroTech Innovation Day, European Week of Cities and Regions (Brussel, Belgium)
Global	Same as European events but should include more emphasis on the concept of ERA hubs in order for	All project partners keep an eye on international/global opportunities and participation	e.g. WOIC, November 2023 (Bilbao, Spain)

	non-Europeans to understand.	will be done by rep. from COOPERATE project	
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6 Measurement, Scheduling and Evaluation

Measurement, scheduling, and evaluation are integral aspects to reach the goals and objectives of the COOPERATE project and to achieve a reach beyond the consortium and the duration of the project. They ensure that content efforts are well-planned, effectively executed, and continuously improved..

6.1 Measurement of success of communication efforts and impact

To help determine COOPERATE's impact to understand the effects of the project on stakeholders and the general public, measurable values – or Key Performance Indicators (KPI)– must be set. KPIs will show which communication channels are reaching its intended targets and highlight underperforming elements of the strategy. The performance of this strategy's key elements will be measured quarterly by tracking the following:

1. **Online communication** – Analytical web tools for monitoring traffic on the website and social network platforms will give insight into the demographics of visitors, their interests and needs. They will also indicate the level of engagement through comments and post sharing.
2. **Project documentation** – How many times has COOPERATE been mentioned in or interviewed for articles or publications? Has COOPERATE been mentioned in or interviewed for television or podcasts? Etc.
3. **Outreach Initiatives** – In how many events did we participate and present the project? Is the number of attendees growing as the project moves forward? How much support and participants are gained after these public gatherings?

6.2 Content calendar and schedule

Table 3: Content calendar, schedule, KPI and measuring tools

Activity	When	Target Aud.	KPI	Measuring Tool
Branding and logos	Project start	All	/	/
Online communication				
Website	Updated continuously	All	> 750 visitors by month 8 > 1.500 visitors by month 16 > 2.250 visitors by month 24 > 3000 visitors by month 30	Online Analytical Tools
LinkedIn	Updated continuously: Min. 2 posts per month linked to relevant topic	All	> 200 followers by month 8 > 400 followers by month 16 > 600 followers by month 24 > 1000 followers by month 30	Online Analytical Tools

	or interesting for audience			
Quarterly Newsletters	Every three months 1. March 2023 2. June 2023 3. September 2023 4. December 2023 5. March 2024 6. June 2024 7. September 2024 8. December 2024 9. March 2025 10. June 2025	All	> 50 individuals by month 8 > 100 individ. by month 16 > 150 individ. by month 24 > 200 individ. by month 30	Online Analytical Tools
Project Documentation				
Communication kit	Midterm	All	> 400 downloads	Online Analytical Tools
Press Release	Press releases will be sent to media outlets to announce important news about the project	Media outlets	/	/
Videos	1) midterm, 2) before or after events, 3) at the end to present results	All	> 3.000 views by month 30	Performance registry
White paper	At the end of the project	Government and academia	/	/
Outreach Initiatives				
Expert talks and podcasts	Continuously when possible and relevant	non-scientific stakeholders	no. of expert talks and podcasts: 6	/
Events	All project partners keep an eye on opportunities and participation will be done by rep. from COOPERATE project	Stakeholders who can give feedback for the piloting work and recommendations	no. of webinars/seminars: 3 no. of events with 200+ participants: 2	Attendance registry

6.3 Regular evaluation and adjustments to the communication and outreach strategy

Evaluation is the cornerstone of a successful communication and outreach strategy. It is the basis on which to assess whether the COOPERATE communication and outreach process contributes to achieve the global project goals and objectives. Assessment of communication activities will be performed parallel to the project's overall assessment and evaluation. The purpose is to regularly re-examine the strategy to find underperforming elements, redefine where necessary and continue monitoring to ensure its success. An evaluation of this communication strategy will be carried out as follows: by assessing performance standards; measuring impact, performance registry and reporting, re-examining and reinforce messages.

It is the responsibility of every consortium member to keep records of their own communication and dissemination activities in order to track target numbers accurately and assist in impact measurement. Registry forms will be available in SharePoint to track communication activities undertaken by each consortium member. These will be forwarded to the WP5 lead (BRAIN). Assessment of the communication strategy will take place on a semi-annually basis.

7 Conclusions

This document shows the importance of a communication and outreach strategy in order to achieve the objectives and goals set by the project. In order to connect and engage with a specific target audience several activities are needed and require a broad set of stakeholders to participate. A collective effort is needed to achieve the projects goals and objectives.

This strategic document is directly linked to the operationalisation of D5.1 "Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results Release I". It provides the strategic basis and framework within which the various actions and activities will be deployed and presents more thorough insights regarding the stakeholders and target audiences that COOPERATE will aim to address, reach and engage with for the effective implementation, deployment and roll-out of the ERA-Hub concept across Europe. Through regular monitoring, the project team will be able to evaluate the effectiveness and efficacy of this Communication and Outreach Strategy and make adjustments when and where necessary to ensure that the set goals, objectives and target indicators are met successfully.

8 Appendix

8.1 Consortium Partner Websites and Social Network Handles

TU/e	Technische Universiteit Eindhoven	
Website	https://www.tue.nl/en/	
LinkedIn	linkedin.com/school/eindhoven-university-of-technology	
Twitter	twitter.com/TUeindhoven	
Facebook	facebook.com/TU.Eindhoven	
Instagram	instagram.com/tueindhoven	
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/tueindhoven	

STAM	Stam S.r.l.	
Website	www.stamtech.com	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/Stam-s-r-l	
Twitter	@Stam_Tech	
Facebook		
Instagram		
YouTube		

BRAIN	Brainport Development NV	
Website	www.brainporteindhoven.com/en	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/brainport-development	
Twitter	@Brainport_int	
Facebook	@BrainportEindhoven	
Instagram	@brainporteindhoven	
YouTube	https://youtube.com/user/brainport	

CVUT	Ceske Vysoke Uceni Technicke V Praze	
Website	https://www.cvut.cz/	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/cvutpraha/	
Twitter	https://twitter.com/CVUTPraha/	
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CVUTPraha/	
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/cvutpraha/	

YouTube	
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DTU	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	
Website	www.skylab.dtu.dk	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/dtuskylab	
Twitter	https://twitter.com/DTUSkylab?s=20	
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/dtuskylab	
Instagram	dtuskylab	
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCFc8U1OknoqZqn0jGqd0nuA	

IDEA	Idea Strategische Economische Consulting	
Website	www.ideaconsult.be	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/68507/	
Twitter		
Facebook		
Instagram		
YouTube		

LYNGBY	Science City Lyngby	
Website	https://vidensby.dk/en/home/	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/science-city-lyngby/	
Twitter		
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Vidensbyen/	
Instagram		
YouTube		